

Site: SPHINX TEMPLE Season '80Area: N. Collunade Square R16 Locus Number (2) LEVEL 2

January 7, 1980

Progress of Excavation Beginning at approx 27 cm an area of clean yellow sand was present. This is to be designated as Level 3. Mark suggested that this sand may be fill from a previous excavation and that the hard packed light brown sand to Rock of Level 4 is the undisturbed area. Note that Level 3 appears to extend down the slope of the trench and at app 60 cm along G/S/S/R16/2 the soil above the clean sand is more humified. It should be noted scraps of modern newsprint were uncovered. Level 3 lenses under the area of dk brown soil of Level one. In a section into this dk brown soil there were pieces of newspaper and by amt of decayed limestone.

Locus Description Level two - light brown sand w/ fragments of limestone.

Location in Square _____

Under Locus _____ Over Locus _____

Locus Dimensions 2 m 70 X 1 m

Levels _____

Analysis of non-artifactual materials _____